

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of some Adducts of Chlorobis(dialkyldithiocarbamato)antimony(III) with Nitrogen Bases

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Adducts of the type $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2 \cdot \text{B}$ (where $\text{R}_2 = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2, (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2, (\text{CH}_2)_5$ and $\text{B} = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}, \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$) have been prepared in dichloromethane under strictly anhydrous conditions at room temperature. These monomeric compounds have been characterised by elemental analyses, ir and ^1H nmr spectral studies. The dithiocarbamate moieties are chelating in all these complexes and coordination number around antimony(III) is generally six except in case of 1 10-phenanthroline adducts for which it appears to be seven

ANTIMONY(III)¹⁻⁴ as well as antimony(v) halides^{5,6} form a wide range of solid adducts with nitrogen bases. However, little attention has been paid on the Lewis acidic character of well-known halodithiocarbamate derivatives of antimony(III), $[\text{XSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2]^{7-9}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or I) although crystal structures of $\text{Sb}[(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)_2\text{I}]\cdot\text{CHCl}_3$ ¹⁰ and $\text{Sb}[\text{S}_2\text{CNBu}_2][\text{Cd}_2\text{I}_6]$ ¹¹ have been reported.

We report herein synthesis, physicochemical properties and tentative structures of some adducts of chlorobis(dialkyldithiocarbamato)antimony(III) with nitrogen bases.

Experimental

Solvents were dried and purified by standard methods¹². Antimony(III) chloride was distilled (78°/10 mm) before use. Molecular weights of the derivatives were determined in chloroform using a Knauer vapour pressure osmometer. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer in DMSO-d_6 using TMS as an external standard.

As all the derivatives of the types, $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2$ ⁹ and $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2 \cdot \text{B}$ have been synthesised by a similar procedure and synthesis of only one representative is described below.

Synthesis of $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)_2$: A solution of diethylamine (3.14 g, 42.93 mmol) in methanol (~ 10 ml) was slowly added to a solution of antimony trichloride (2.44 g, 10.70 mmol) and carbon disulphide (1.63 g, 21.41 mmol) in methanol (~30 ml) around ~0° with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 2 h and the resulting solid was dissolved in dichloromethane. The solution was then concentrated by distilling the excess solvent under reduced pressure and precipitation was induced by the addition of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) to get

yellowish white chlorobis(diethyldithiocarbamato)-antimony(III). The product was further recrystallised from dichloromethane and dried under reduced pressure, (3.88 g, 80%) (Table 1).

Synthesis of $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Et}_3\text{N}$: A solution of triethylamine (0.56 g, 5.53 mol) in dichloromethane (~ 10 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of chlorobis(diethyldithiocarbamato)-antimony(III) (2.50 g, 5.51 mmol) in dichloromethane (~ 10 ml) at room temperature. The resulting yellow precipitate was washed with dichloromethane and n-hexane and dried under reduced pressure, (2.6 g, 85 %) (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The reaction of antimony(III) chloride with carbon disulphide and the secondary amine or piperidine in 1 : 2 : 4 molar ratio in methanol under anhydrous conditions, yields $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2$,

where, $\text{R}_2 = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2, (\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2, (\text{CH}_2)_5$. All the three products are yellowish white solids, which depict monomeric behaviour in chloroform. Reactions of $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2$ in dichloromethane with nitrogen bases (B) in 1 : 1 molar ratio give adducts of the type $\text{ClSb}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)_2 \cdot \text{B}$,

where, $\text{B} = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}, \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2$. All these adducts are yellow to orange solids and are moderately soluble in chloroform and dimethylsulphoxide. These have been further purified by recrystallisation from dichloromethane. The compounds are hygroscopic in nature and tend to decompose on heating even under reduced pressure. All the adducts are

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Mol. weight Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
			Sb	S	N	Cl
1.	CISb(S ₂ CNEt ₂) ₂	437 (454)	26.31 (26.83)	27.96 (28.26)	5.97 (6.17)	7.28 (7.81)
2.	CISb(S ₂ CN dip.) ₂	515 (510)	23.30 (23.88)	24.68 (25.15)	5.00 (5.49)	6.41 (6.95)
3.	CISb(S ₂ CN pip.) ₂	456 (478)	25.09 (25.48)	26.61 (26.84)	—	7.33 (7.42)
4.	CISb(S ₂ CNEt ₂) ₂ .Et ₃ N	523 (555)	21.65 (21.94)	23.06 (23.11)	7.33 (7.57)	6.06 (6.39)
5.	CISb(S ₂ CNEt ₂) ₂ .Py	520 (533)	22.53 (22.85)	23.93 (24.07)	—	6.48 (6.65)
6.	CISb(S ₂ CNEt ₂) ₂ .Phen	657 (634)	19.02 (19.20)	20.07 (20.23)	—	5.23 (5.59)
7.	CISb(S ₂ CN dip.) ₂ .Et ₃ N	637 (611)	19.65 (19.92)	20.80 (20.99)	6.56 (6.88)	5.58 (5.80)
8.	CISb(S ₂ CN dip.) ₂ .Py	555 (589)	20.41 (20.67)	21.61 (21.77)	—	5.86 (6.02)
9.	CISb(S ₂ CN dip.) ₂ .Phen	712 (690)	17.48 (17.64)	18.36 (18.58)	—	5.01 (5.14)
10.	CISb(S ₂ CN pip.) ₂ .Et ₃ N	537 (579)	20.80 (21.03)	22.08 (22.15)	—	6.07 (6.12)
11.	CISb(S ₂ CN pip.) ₂ .Py	526 (557)	21.50 (21.86)	22.99 (23.03)	—	6.15 (6.37)
12.	CISb(S ₂ CN pip.) ₂ .Phen	645 (658)	18.23 (18.50)	19.29 (19.49)	—	5.22 (5.39)

*Et₂=diethyl, dip=dipropyl, pip=ptperidyl, Et₃N=triethylamine, Py=pyridine, Phen=1,10-phenanthroline.

TABLE 2—IR AND ¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES CISb(S₂CNR₂)₂ AND CISb(S₂CNR₂)₂.B

Sl. no.	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)			δ								
	Dithiocarbamate (C=N)	Nitrogen bases (C=S)	(Sb-N)	Dithiocarbamate moiety				Nitrogen bases				
				CH ₃	CH ₂	CH ₂			CH ₃	CH ₂	Aromatic	
1.	1 492vs	985s	—	1.36(t)	3.74(q)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.	1 495s	980vs	—	0.88(t)	1.67(m)	3.65(m)	—	—	—	—	—	—
3.	1 495vs	992s	—	—	—	—	1.58(s) (b,c)	3.92(su) (a)	—	—	—	—
4.	1 490s	985s	397w	1.19(t)	3.74(q)	—	—	—	1.19(t)	2.99(q)	—	—
5.	1 490s	992s	405w	1.36(t)	3.83(q)	—	—	—	—	—	6.03-7.35(m)	—
6.	1 490vs	980s	415w	1.36(t)	3.83(q)	—	—	—	—	—	7.20-9.40(m)	—
7.	1 510s	980s	399w	0.88(t)	1.67(m)	3.65(m)	—	—	1.14(t)	3.08(q)	—	—
8.	1 490s	1 000vs	405w	0.88(t)	1.67(m)	3.65(m)	—	—	—	—	6.50-8.50(m)	—
9.	1 485s	1 015s	415w	0.88(t)	1.67(m)	3.65(m)	—	—	—	3.08(q)	7.30-9.40(m)	—
10.	1 487s	1 000s	402w	—	—	—	1.67(s) (b,c)	3.92(su) (a)	1.23(t)	—	—	—
11.	1 490vs	980vs	405w	—	—	—	1.58(s) (b,c)	3.92(su) (a)	—	—	6.50-8.50(m)	—
12.	1 498s	980vs	415w	—	—	—	1.58(s) (b,c)	3.92(su) (a)	—	—	7.50-9.40(m)	—

*Compounds same as in Table 1.

vs=very strong, s=strong, m=medium, w=weak ; s=singlet, t=triplet, q=quartet, m=multiplet, u=unresolved.

monomeric in chloroform. Molar conductivity values (2-4 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in DMSO of the adducts suggest that they are essentially covalent in nature.

The assignments of significant ir bands in the spectra of these derivatives have been made on the basis of published work on related antimony compounds^{7,13-15} (Table 2). Generally the spectra of the complexes with bidentate dithiocarbamate

groups⁷ depict single bands at ~1 500 and ~1 000 cm⁻¹ for C=N and C=S absorptions respectively, whereas the complexes with monodentate dithiocarbamate groups show doublets at ~1 470 and ~1 070 cm⁻¹ for the two modes of vibrations. All the complexes of antimony(III) show single band at 1 485-1 510 and 980-1 015 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to $\nu_{C=N}$ and $\nu_{C=S}$ vibrations respectively, suggesting bidentate nature of the dithiocarbamate groups in these complexes.

The spectrum of free triethylamine shows bands in the regions 2 960–2 800 (CH) and 1 425–1 410 cm^{-1} (C–N), however, in the adducts these bands are observed at 3 000–2 830 and 1 460–1 420 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating coordination of triethylamine to antimony(III).

Coordination of pyridine in the adducts is indicated by the upfield shift of various bands present in the free pyridine¹³, such as 1 575–1 620 (C=C) and 1 430–1 460 cm^{-1} (C=N). A weak band near 405 cm^{-1} in these adducts may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sb-N}}$ vibration.

The infrared stretching frequencies of 1,10-phenanthroline¹⁴ are shifted to higher frequencies on adduct formation, particularly in the region 1 400–1 650 cm^{-1} (C=C and C=N ring stretching). A weak band near 415 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{Sb-N}}$ vibration is also observed. Shifts of various bands of free 1,10-phenanthroline to higher frequencies on adduct formation suggest bidentate nature of the 1,10-phenanthroline ligand.

¹H nmr spectral data of these adducts have been recorded at room temperature (Table 2). The ¹H nmr signals of various dithiocarbamate moieties in these adducts appear without any appreciable shifts from the reported values on related antimony(III) dithiocarbamate complexes^{7,8}. A comparison of the spectra of free Lewis bases (triethylamine, pyridine¹⁶, 1,10-phenanthroline) with the spectra of the corresponding adducts indicates an upfield shift of various signals (Table 2). For example, a shift of aromatic protons (δ 6.03–8.50) has been observed in the case of pyridine adducts as compared with those of the free ligand (δ 7.17–9.11), whereas in case of 1,10-phenanthroline, the aromatic protons undergo downfield shift to δ 7.20–9.40 as compared with those of the free ligand (δ 6.86–8.54), suggesting coordination of the nitrogen in all the above derivatives.

Although the actual structures can be established only after X-ray analysis, yet the available physico-chemical data suggest the following type of structure for these adducts,

where, $R_2 = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2, (\text{C}_6\text{H}_7)_2, (\text{CH}_2)_6, R' = (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$.

in which the effective coordination around antimony(III) is six. In the 1,10-phenanthroline adducts, antimony(III) may be seven-coordinated. The active lone-pair of antimony(III) in the coordination sphere has not been taken into consideration in the structure suggested above.

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